

DISORDER OF THE MENSTRUAL CYCLE

Teachers of the Technical College of Public Health

named after Abu Ali ibn Sino

Abbosxo'jayeva Marhabo

To'laganova Nigora

Abstract: The rhythmic repeating processes in the female body associated with hormones and accompanied by menstrual bleeding are called the menstrual cycle.

Key words: menstrual cycle, period, vagina, uterus, female

During the menstrual cycle, changes occur in a woman's body aimed at providing the necessary conditions for the beginning of pregnancy and its completion. The formation of menstrual function depends on the period of puberty. Usually, menarche (first menstruation) is observed at the age of 11-14 years, after which the regularity of the menstrual cycle is established in the period from 1 to 1.5 years.

Causes of menstrual cycle disorders

NORMAL MENSTRUAL CYCLE

menstruation (menstruation) to the first day of the next menstruation. According to individual physiology, the menstrual cycle normally lasts from 21 to 30-35 days, usually 28 days. Loss of menstrual function occurs during menopause - between 45-50 years of age.

Regulation of the menstrual cycle occurs under the influence of a complex neurohumoral mechanism, which is carried out by the cerebral cortex, pituitary gland, hypothalamus, ovaries and is carried out with the benefit of the vagina, uterus and mammary glands.

The gonadotropic hormones FSG, LG and LTG secreted by the hypothalamus-pituitary system cause changes in the ovaries, which is called the ovarian cycle and includes the following steps:

Follicular phase — the process of follicle maturation;

Ovulation phase — the rupture of a mature follicle and the release of an egg cell;

Progesterone (lutein) phase is the process of corpus luteum development.

Normal menstrual cycle

At the end of the menstrual cycle, if the egg cell is not fertilized, the corpus luteum regresses. Ovarian sex hormones (estrogens, progestogens) cause changes in tone, blood supply, excitability, dynamic processes in the mucous membrane of the uterus, that is, the uterine cycle consists of two stages:

The proliferation phase is the recovery of the functional layer of the endometrium, healing of the damaged surface and its further development. This stage occurs simultaneously with the development of the follicle.

Secretion phase — softening, thickening and rejection (desquamation) of the functional layer of the uterine mucosa. Rejection of the functional layer is manifested by menstruation. In terms of time, this stage corresponds to the development and death of the corpus luteum in the ovary.

Thus, the menstrual cycle is usually divided into two phases: the follicular and luteal phases of the ovarian cycle and the corresponding proliferative and secretory phases of the uterine cycle. As a rule, the above-mentioned cyclical processes are repeated again and again at certain time intervals during the entire fertile age of a woman.

CAUSES OF DISRUPTION OF THE MENSTRUAL CYCLE

Disruption of the menstrual cycle is not a disease, but a sign of disturbances in the functioning of internal organs.

The causes of menstrual dysfunction may be different, in particular:

Gynecological diseases (myoma and cancer of the uterus, inflammation of the uterus and appendages);

Severe extragenital diseases (blood diseases, endocrine system, liver, central nervous system diseases, heart defects);

Infections;

Hypovitaminosis;

Sudden change of residence;

Traumatic damage to the uterus (in instrumental manipulations - abortion, etc.);

Not getting enough sleep;

Stress and mental trauma.

Cycle disruption can also be triggered by other organs and systems, such as:

Lose a lot of weight in a short period of time;

diabetes mellitus;

Hypertension;

Pathologies of the thyroid gland;

Obesity;

Adrenal gland disorders;

Acceptance of certain types of drugs.

TYPES OF MENSTRUAL DISORDER

Disruption of the menstrual cycle can be manifested by changes in the rhythm and intensity of menstruation, for example, lengthening or shortening of the period between them, increasing or decreasing the amount of secreted blood, changing the menstrual rhythm. Disruption of the menstrual cycle occurs in the following form:

Amenorrhea - absence of menstruation for more than 6 months;

Hypermenstrual syndrome:

hypermenorrhea - excessive menstrual blood;

polymenorrhea - menstruation for more than 7 days;

Proyomenorrhoea - frequent menstruation with an interval of less than 21 days.

Hypomenstrual syndrome:

hypomenorrhea - lack of menstrual blood;

oligomenorrhea - shortening of the menstrual period (no more than 1-2 days);

opsomenorrhoea - menstruation with very long intervals of 35 days or more.

Algomenorrhea - painful menstruation;

Dysmenorrhea is menstruation accompanied by general disorders (headache, loss of appetite, nausea, vomiting);

Algodysmenorrhea - menstruation accompanied by local pains and worsening of the general condition;

Anovulator, which occurs as a result of a violation of neuroendocrine regulation, characterized by the absence of ovulation and corpus luteum (one-phase) uterine bleeding.

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